

ENHANCING THE INTERFACIAL ADHESION VIA CHEMICAL GRAFTING MULTILAYER POLYETHER AMINE/GO ON CARBON FIBER SURFACE

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ABSTRACT

Inspired by the hard/soft phase combined structures of biological and natural materials, nano-structured polyether amine/GO (DG for short) multilayers were attached onto carbon fiber surface by chemical grafting approach. Scanning electron microscopy reveals the uniform coverage of DG multilayer on fiber surface, and the compactness and thickness of this coverage increase with increasing layers from 1 (CF-DG) to 4 (CF-DG4). The detected oxygen gradually increases with enhancing grafting layers, which leads to enhanced polar component of surface energy. Simultaneously, the wettability of fiber with resin improves corresponding with increased grafting layers. After modification, the interfacial shear strength of CF-DG, CF-DG2 and CF-DG4 are improved 7.7%, 18.8% and 60.0% as compared with untreated CF, and the improving efficiency is most outstanding for reinforcement with 4 layers (CF-DG4). This outcome can be ascribed to: i) brick-and-mortar structure is formed on fiber surface when the layer number reaches 4, where platelet structured GO acts as a role to increase strength, deflect cracks and redistribute stress, while polyether amine acts as a role to interlock with GO and provide a soft phase to allow movements of GO sheets; ii) the abundant active groups on CF-DG4 surface can improve the wettability and form strong chemical bonds with epoxy matrix; iii) the uniform coverage of multilayers could effectively avoid stress concentration.

1 INTRODUCTION

Excellent properties such as high specific strength and stiffness, satisfactory fatigue and corrosion resistance, good thermal stability make carbon fiber reinforced polymer composites (CFRPs) ideal structural materials to be used in the industries of aerospace, transportation, energy, and sports equipment [1, 2]. A great limitation of CFRPs is their interphase between fiber and resin, which has a vital role in controlling the overall behavior of the composite [3]. However, the pristine surface of carbon fiber is generally non-polar and inert, which greatly weaken the interfacial adhesion. Therefore, numerous methods [4-6], including oxidation, chemical grafting, plasma treatment, high-energy irradiation and self-assembly, have been proposed to activate the fiber surface and thus improve the interfacial adhesion of the resulting composites. Among all the methods, chemical grafting can create chemical bonds at interphase, which is effective to obtain an appropriate interphase.

Biological and natural materials, such as nacre [7] and bone [8], are good examples for having prominent mechanical properties. One reason for this is the hierarchical architecture comprising a hard phase to provide strength and a soft phase to allow movement between nanolamellas or nanoparticles [9-11]. GO is one of the most desirable nanomaterials that has abundant highly reactive oxygen groups on its basal planes and edges [12, 13], which could afford active sites for further functionalization and thus increase the interactions with modified carbon fibers and/or host resin matrix. Moreover, the large specific area, high strength and flexibility can increase mechanical interlocking and deviate cracks in composites [14]. Considering this, GO is considered to be an ideal material as the hard phase. Polyether amine has two amino groups at the end of its molecule, which could promote its interactions

with GO during composite manufacture. Moreover, its flexible molecule structure could facilitate the movement between GO sheets and improve the energy dissipation during deformation of interphase [15, 16]. Thus, polyether amine could be selected as the soft phase.

In this work, nano-structured polyether amine/GO multilayers were attached onto carbon fiber surface by chemical grafting approach, and their impacts on interfacial shear strengths (IFSSs) of composites were compared. The resulting composites exhibit great enhancement in IFSSs, especially for reinforcement with 4 polyether amine/GO layers. The surface physicochemical properties of carbon fibers were studied and the detailed enhancement mechanisms were explored. This provides a new strategy to obtain high quality composites with great interfacial bonding.

2 EXPERIMENTAL

2.1 Materials

Carbon fibers with diameter of about 5.5 μm were supplied from TORAY, Japan. Polyether amine was supplied by Wuxi Singmen Electronic Materials Co. Ltd. GO was purchased from Xiamen Knano Graphene Technology Corporation Limited. 5228 epoxy matrix was offered by Beijing Institute of Aeronautical Materials, China. The recommended curing process of 5228 is as follow: 1 h at 130°C, then, 2 h at 180°C, then, 3 h at 190°C. Dimethylformamide (DMF), nitric acid (HNO_3) and dichloromethane were respectively procured from Tianjin Tianli Chemical Reagent Co. Ltd, Sichuan Xilong Chemical Co. Ltd and Tianjin Fuyu Chemical Co., Ltd. Formamide, acetone, diiodomethane and thionyl chloride (SOCl_2) were purchased from Sinopharm Chemical Reagent Co. Ltd.

2.2 Chemical grafting polyether amine/GO onto carbon fiber

Prior to use, sizing agent and pollutants of fibers were removed by acetone at 80°C for 24 h using Soxhlet method, and the obtained fibers were marked as CF. Then, the oxidation of CF was conducted by HNO_3 at 80°C for 4 h, followed by further acylation reacted with SOCl_2 at 70°C for 24 h with reference to Ma. et al [17].

After acylation, the fibers were placed in a polyether amine/DMF (1/10 by volume) mixture and the reaction was carried out at 90°C for 24 h. Then, the fibers were further immersed into the uniformly dispersed GO(0.1 g)/DMF(100 ml) solution and cryogenically sonicated for 1 h, followed by 90°C/24h treatment to complete GO grafting. After cleaning by deionized water and drying under vacuum, the product was designated as CF-DG. Following the same modification process, the chemical grafting of polyether amine and GO were repeated once and three times to acquire the final samples, which were denoted as CF-DG2 and CF-DG4.

2.3 Characterization

Surface morphologies of fibers were investigated using HTACHIS-4800 scanning electron microscopy (SEM) with a 5 kV accelerating voltage. Raman spectrum was acquired using Renishaw-invia Microscopes Raman Spectrometer with 532 nm laser excitation. Fourier Transform Infrared Spectrometer (FTIR, Bruker-Vector 22) spectra of fibers were obtained using powder pressed KBr pellets in the wavenumber range of 400~4000 cm^{-1} with a spectral resolution of 4 cm^{-1} . X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) was performed on an ESCALAB 250Xi (ThermoFisher, United States) with a monochromatic Al $K\alpha$ X-ray source at 225 W under the base pressure of lower than 2×10^{-9} mbar. The curve fitting and data analysis of the C1s spectra were calibrated upon C 1s peak at 284.8 eV as reference. The wettability of carbon fibers were investigated by a dynamic contact angle instrument (DCAT21, Data-physics). The surface energy was calculated on the basis of OWRK method [18], using three testing liquids, respectively deionized water, formamide and diiodomethane. IFSS was evaluated by micro-debonding tests on Japan's East Wing Industrial device-MODEL HM410 at a motion speed of 0.03 mm/min with sensitivity of 1/100 gf. The epoxy micro droplets within lengths of 30~60 μm were selected for the test. IFSS was calculated using the following relationship:

$$\tau_{IFSS} = \frac{F}{\pi dl} \quad (1)$$

where F is the peak pullout force, l is the embedded length of the resin droplet, and d is the average diameter of the fiber. Each final IFSS value was the average of at least 20 times of valid measurements.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Effects of multilayer on physical properties of fibers

Surface morphologies of different fibers were observed by SEM, as shown in Figure 1. Obviously rough surface with lots of deep grooves distributed along fiber axial can be seen for non-decorated CF (Figure 1a). For CF-DG, thin and transparent GO sheets are observed on fiber surface (Figure 1b). When the DG layers increase to 2, more GO sheets can be found, however, they are not evenly distributed on fiber surface (Figure 1c). When the DG layers further increase to 4, compact and homogeneous GO coatings that create corrugated textures are noticed on fiber surface (Figure 1d). The surface structures of fibers were studied by Raman, as displayed in Figure 2a. Quantification of the intensity ratio of D band to G band (I_D/I_G) reveals the degree of the functionalization and the extent of structural defects in modified fibers. Compared to CF ($I_D/I_G=0.914$), I_D/I_G values of modified fibers show an gradual enhancement from 0.935 of CF-DG to 0.959 of CF-DG4, indicating the growing degree of functionalization and the formation of chemical bonds between polyether amine and GO [19].

Figure 1: Surface morphologies of (a) CF, (b) CF-DG, (c) CF-DG2, and (d) CF-DG4.

The surface energy of carbon fiber, including its polar (γ^p) and dispersive (γ^d) components, which were determined via the dynamic contact angles (CAs) between single fibers and three testing liquids, could reflect the wettability and the interfacial adhesion. The results are shown in Figure 2b. After functionalization, the γ^p increases corresponding to the increased grafting cycle, which may be explained from the growth in functional groups of polyether amine and GO. For γ^d of modified fibers, it tends to go up first to 18.92 mJ/m² of CF-DG2 and then go down to 17.60 mJ/m² of CF-DG4. The increased γ^d is probably attributed to the increased surface roughness, while for CF-DG4, more and uniform GO coverage on fiber surface adversely decrease the surface roughness. This results are consistent with fiber morphologies in Figure 1.

Figure 2: Raman spectra (a) and surface energy (b) of different fibers

3.2 Effects of multilayer on chemical properties of fibers

FTIR spectra of different fibers are shown in Figure 3a. For CF, the bands at 3440 cm^{-1} and 1638 cm^{-1} are ascribed to -OH and C=C stretching vibrations. After functionalization, the bands appear at 1741 cm^{-1} and 1225 cm^{-1} are assigned to C=O and C-O stretching vibrations. Moreover, the bands at about 2921 cm^{-1} and 2855 cm^{-1} belong to $\text{-CH}_2\text{-}$ vibration. These indicates the successful grafting of GO on fiber surface through polyether amine. Moreover, the broader overlapping peak of hydroxyl and amino groups at 3453 cm^{-1} is observed for CF-DG4.

Figure 3: FTIR (a) and XPS wide-scan spectra (b) of different fibers

Carbon fiber	Element and its content(%)			
	C/(1s=284.8 eV)	O/(1s=531.0 eV)	N/(1s=398.1 eV)	Si/(2p=101 eV)
CF	79.71	14.07	1.97	4.25
CF-DG	72.74	19.95	3.63	3.68
CF-DG2	75.59	19.99	2.99	1.43
CF-DG4	68.3	25.27	2.73	3.7

Table 1: Element and its content on fiber surface detected by XPS

XPS was employed to clarify the surface chemical composition of fibers. As shown in Figure 3b, C1s, N1s and O1s, respectively at binding energy of 284 eV, 398 eV and 531 eV, are revealed for all fibers. The detected oxygen gradually increases with enhancing grafting layers, while the content of nitrogen decreases (Table 1), implying the improving GO sheets on fiber surface with increasing layers. The high-resolution C1s spectra of different fibers are displaced in Figure 4. The C1s spectrum

for CF in Figure 4a has three pronounced peaks at 284.8 eV (C-C), 286.4eV (C-OH, C-O-C) and 288.8eV(HO-C=O). After grafting one polyether amine/GO layer, there appears two new peaks at 285.3 eV and 287.9 eV, which are separately assigned to the C-N and generated HN-C=O bonds [20, 21]. Simultaneously, the peak representative of HO-C=O at 288.8 eV vanishes and the content of C-O-C peak decreases from 24.05% of CF to 14.61%. These again prove the existence of covalent bonds for CF-DG2. For CF-DG2 and CF-DG4 in Figure 4c and 4d, the HN-C=O peak disappears and the HO-C=O peak appears again, which may be caused by more GO sheets adhered on fiber surfaces.

Figure 4: XPS high-resolution C1s spectra of (a) CF, (b) CF-DG, (c) CF-DG2, and (d) CF-DG4.

3.3 Interfacial shear strength

First, CAs between fibers and matrix were evaluated in Figure 5a. In comparison with CF, CAs decrease for CF-DG, CF-DG2 and CF-DG4, and the last has the lowest CA of 55°, indicating improved wettability after fiber modification, especially for CF-DG4. The improved wettability is favorable for molecular diffusion and subsequent chemical interactions between fiber and matrix.

IFSSs of different fiber composites were presented in Figure 5b. IFSS of CF composites is 69.8MPa, while IFSSs of CF-DG, CF-DG2 and CF-DG4 are 75.2 MPa, 82.9 MPa and 111.7 MPa, respectively increase 7.7%, 18.8% and 60%. The improved IFSSs could be attributed to the following aspects: First, the improved wettability of resin with fibers could promote resin molecular diffusion to the surface of fibers and enhance the chemical bonds between fibers and matrix, which is favorable for stress transfer. Second, the large specific surface area and wrinkled structure of GO could consume more energy to pull the modified fibers from the matrix. Third, the polyether amine could suffer from higher deformation, which is in favor of energy dissipation during deformation.

Comparing the effects of grafting layers on IFSS, the improving efficiency is most outstanding for reinforcement with 4 layers. This outcome can be ascribed to: i) brick-and-mortar structure is formed on fiber surface when the layer number reaches 4, where platelet structured GO acts as a role to increase strength, deflect cracks and redistribute stress, while polyether amine acts as a role to interlock with GO and provide a soft phase to allow movements of GO sheets; ii) the abundant active

groups on CF-DG4 surface can improve the wettability and form strong chemical bonds with epoxy matrix; iii) the uniform coverage of multilayers could effectively avoid stress concentration.

Figure 5: Contact angle (CA) and IFSSs of fiber with epoxy resin

4 CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, polyether amine/GO multilayers were attached onto carbon fiber surface by chemical grafting approach, and its effects on interfacial adhesion were investigated. The resulting hierarchical composites all presented higher IFSSs than untreated CF composites, and the highest IFSS is achieved for CF-DG4. The enhancement mechanisms of interfacial adhesion were explored in details. This work provides a new strategy that high quality composites with great interfacial bonding can be realized.

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